

GENERAL INFORMATION AND THEORIES ABOUT PSYCHODRAMA

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Abstract. This study discusses psychological analyses based on historical data about psychodrama. The origins of psychodrama and the main content of the methods used in psychological training are discussed. Also, during our study, based on modern psychological research by experienced educational psychologists, the application of the concept of psychodrama in psychology and the essence of psychodrama are explained in detail.

Keywords: Psychodrama, psychological approaches, Moreno's theory, psychological methods, psychological training, history of psychodrama.

PSIXODRAMA HAQIDA UMUMIY MA'LUMOTLAR VA NAZARIYALAR

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqotda psixodrama haqida tarixiy ma'lumotlarga asoslangan psixologik tahlillar haqida muhokama qilinadi. Psixodramaning kelib chiqishi va psixologik treninglarda qo'llanilish metodlarining asosiy mazmuni haqida aytib o'tiladi. Shuningdek, tadqiqotimiz davomida tajribali pedagog-psixologlarning zamonaviy psixologik tadqiqotlariga asoslangan holda, psixodrama tushunchasining psixologiyada qo'llanilishi va psixodramaning mohiyati haqida batafsil tushuntirib o'tiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Psixodrama, psixologik yondashuvlar, Moreno nazariyasi, psixologik metodlar, psixologik treninglar, psixodrama tarixi.

ОБЩАЯ ИНФОРМАЦИЯ И ТЕОРИИ О ПСИХОДРАМЕ

Аннотация. В настоящем исследовании представлен психологический анализ, основанный на исторических данных о психодраме. Рассматриваются истоки психодрамы и основное содержание методов, используемых в психологическом тренинге. Кроме того, в ходе исследования, опираясь на современные психологические исследования опытных педагогов-психологов, подробно излагаются применение концепции психодрамы в психологии и её сущность.

Ключевые слова: Психодрама, психологические подходы, теория Морено, психологические методы, психологический тренинг, история психодрамы.

Introduction

If we look at the history of the development of psychology, we can see that earlier in human psychology, using methods based on psychodrama, the idea of a deeper understanding of the personality, the study of the individual development of the individual, the gradual study of his

inner experiences, the significance of socio-social roles and their mutual psychological relationships was implemented by Moreno. The theory of psychodrama developed by him emerged as a new direction, which allows analyzing the psychology of the individual not only through words, but also through actions, images of psychological development and social scenes.

In the field of psychology, the concept of psychodrama is not only a therapeutic method, but also one of the main psychological directions that helps to understand the social essence of the individual, and is a scientific and practical system aimed at studying the process of individual formation of human roles and self-awareness. According to Moreno, a person is a social being, and in order to fully understand his inner world, it is necessary to relive the experience not only through speech or written expression, but also through action, social roles. This study, based on the practical and theoretical foundations of the theory of psychodrama, analyzes its role in the development of the individual, social mechanisms of understanding social roles, and important aspects of psychological development in the development of the individual. One of the main tasks of the study is to study the scientific justification of Ya.'s psychodrama. Moreno reveals the socio-spiritual development of the individual and its significance in modern psychology. The theoretical foundations of the theory of psychodrama are to create the opportunity to understand the issues of individual development of personality psychology, socio-spiritual characteristics through psychological analysis, sociometry, the theory of social roles, and to gain a deeper understanding of a person's self-awareness and communicative development. In our opinion, this psychological approach reveals the internal mechanisms of the harmonious development of the individual and socio-spiritual aspects of the personality. Psychodrama methods can be used in educational institutions, psychological counseling centers, in the system of socio-spiritual work, in resolving family and interpersonal conflicts. Through it, a person gets the opportunity to express his feelings and form his worldview, establish empathic contact with others, and increase his life experience.

Ya. Moreno considered psychodrama to be the main method that allows a person to find his own identity. Based on the results of his research, he created the theory of psychodrama based on theories that interpret the individual as a socio-psychological system aimed at restoring social activity and mobilizing creative power in his development. The theory of psychodrama developed by Moreno allows a person to develop not only theoretically, but also practically, by helping to analyze roles, reconsider and analyze them, and reveal internal conflicts through the stage.

Therefore, psychodrama is one of the effective psychological methods for analyzing the psychological dynamics of individual development. In order to change a person, it is necessary to return him to his creative stage. This idea fully expresses the essence of psychodrama. For Moreno, the individual development of a person is not considered a passive object of analysis, but is recognized as an active creator of his own life. Therefore, psychodrama is the main psychological direction that helps a person actively understand his role, encourages him to rebuild his life, and helps in choosing social roles. Psychodrama is a major direction in improving the human psyche through its cathartic effect. A person can develop by recognizing and expressing his feelings. Theoretically, a person tries to understand the feelings of others and see himself from the perspective of others (by changing roles). These psychological processes allow a person to constructively solve psychological problems. A person can increase the level of social adaptation to life through social images.

One of the most important psychological concepts in human life is the concept of image.

Ya. L. Moreno, based on the analytical results of the theory of psychodrama, interpreted the social role as a central category. In his opinion, the entire mental state of a person, arising from the process of social activity and self-awareness, is manifested precisely through the system of roles. According to Moreno, from birth, a person gradually assimilates the roles existing in society, adopting some of them, abandoning some, and creatively recreating some. Thus, the "role" is the basic unit that reveals the social content of the human personality. The social image determines the ability of a person to actively participate in the life of society. Each new role means new social experiences for a person, a new stage of growth. Thus, through roles, the socio-spiritual maturity of the individual is formed. A person participating in psychodrama usually experiences the following changes: The ability to understand and express their own feelings increases; People's self-esteem and self-confidence increase; They more clearly understand their social roles and reduce barriers to communicating with others. This helps a person make life decisions. As a result, the individual development of a person is combined with social harmony.

Conclusion

In the process of psychological development, a person begins to perceive himself as an active member of society, develops his creative abilities and becomes a responsible member.

Today, psychodrama is not only a therapeutic tool, but is also widely used in family psychology in such areas as education, leadership, social activity, and upbringing factors. In theories based on psychodrama, we conclude that it is possible to increase a person's life experience by implementing psychological trainings that control his individual development.

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